

GENETIC REGULATIONS OF KHAZMO - AND KLEISTOGAM FLOWER CHARACTERS IN INTERSPECIFIC AND INTERSPECIFIC HYBRIDS

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Annotatsiya: Turlararo va turlararo duragaylardagi hazmo gul belgilarining genetik qonuniyatlari yuqori hosil olish, turli kasalliklar va zararkunandalarga chidamliligi, barglarning tabiiy to'kilishi, tabiiy solinishi va suv tanqisligiga biroz chidamliligi, yuqori tola hosildorligi va uzunligi haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlari: g'o'za, o'simlik, turlararo, xazmogam, kleystogam, gul, belgilari, tezpisharlik, serhosillik, usuv davri, urug'chilik.

Аннотация: Рассмотрены генетические закономерности хазмо- и клейстогамных признаков цветка у межвидовых и межвидовых гибридов по высокой урожайности, высокой устойчивости к различным болезням и вредителям, естественному опадению листьев, естественному увяданию и некоторой устойчивости к недостатку воды, высокому выходу и длине волокна.

Klyuchevye slova: xlochatnik, rastenie, mejvidovoe, xazmogama, kleystogama, svetok, priznaki, skorospelost, fertilst, period sozrevaniya, semena.

Abstract: Genetic laws of hazmo - and kleistogam flower characters in interspecific and interspecific hybrids are considered for high yield, high resistance to various diseases and pests, natural shedding of leaves, natural wilting and some resistance to water shortage, high fiber yield and length.

Keywords: Cotton, plant, interspecific, chasmogama, cleistogama, flower, traits, precocity, fertility, ripening period, seeds.

In cross-species and cross-species hybridization based on the genetic laws of chazmo- and cleistogamous flower characters, the problem of limiting cross-pollination in chazmogamous flowers, and the degree of biological purity existing in their genotypes in the natural state of cleistogamous flower characters, as a task set before the science of selection and seed breeding, which cannot be delayed (95 -98 %) is explained by the association with the most important character and set of complex features for morphobiological and economic with unique information from the organizational point of view, as the main foundation of creating a family, system, gene collection and varieties based on selection multiple times.

In this case, it is very fast ripening, high yield, high resistance to various diseases and pests, including wilt, natural leaf shedding, natural leaf curling and some resistance to water shortage, high fiber yield and high length, meeting the requirements of world standards, the first in the world cotton cultivation practice. used, hermetically closed - cleistogamous flower, the basis of genetic-selection is to create a gene collection and varieties belonging to *G. barbadense* L. type with I "A" industrial type and *G. hirsutum* L. type with III-V industrial type in the homozygous state.

This topic is related to the issue of the problem of genetic control of flower varieties, which is considered an unconventional method, and the chasmogamous and cleistogamous floral characters, which are considered alternative characters, are an absolutely unexplored field in the species range (*G. barbadense* L.), in which, based on the genetic control of the laws of variation and inheritance, these characters It is based on the problems of researching the association with the most important signs and characteristics for the economy and the control of the genetic regularities of the floral signs with the economic signs in interspecies hybridization (*G. hirsutum* L. x *G. barbadense* L.).

Genetic control of chasmogamous and cleistogamous floral characters within the species (*G. hirsutum* L. x *G. hirsutum* L., *G. barbadense* L. x *G. barbadense* L.) and in interspecies hybridization (*G. hirsutum* L. x *G. barbadense* L.) In doing so, it became possible to perform the following tasks in researching its problems for selective purposes.

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